

Synergistic Effects of Bimetallic $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2@ \text{Mn}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ Composites Electrodes for Supercapacitors Applications

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Abstract: The recent high rises in energy crisis worldwide have prompted scientists and scholars to incessantly research on modern energy conversion and storage devices. In this work, the service of composites of transition bimetallic phosphates was employed in the fabrication of electrodes for usages in supercapacitors. The morphology of these electrodes showcases a mixture of leaf, sphere and platelet nanoparticles spread evenly on the surface of the substrate with respect to precursor ratio variations. These fabricated electrodes indicated appreciable crystalline nature from X-ray diffraction results (XRD). Various band gap energies of these electrodes are very low, supporting their excellent electrochemical performance. The excellent charge storage performance of various electrodes were evident from the electrochemical studies and indicate that $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2@ \text{Mn}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ electrodes are potential electrodes for supercapacitors applications. Various electrochemical results clearly designated that bimetallic $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2@ \text{Mn}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ composites formation improved electrodes super capacitive performance and cycle stability. This device can be effectively used in electronics gadgets, hospitals, homes, industries, schools, etc., for energy storing.

Keywords: Supercapacitor, Hydrothermal, Electrodes, Specific Capacitance, Cycle Stability.

Introduction

Modern society's ever-growing demands and newly emerging ecological concerns have prompted research into high-performance, innovative, economical, and ecologically friendly energy-storage technologies (Maaza *et al.*, 2022; Obodo *et al.*, 2024; Obodo *et al.*, 2022). A high power density and high energy are characteristics of the perfect energy-storage device (Ramzan, et al, 2021). Because of a unique charge-storage process, electrochemical supercapacitors (ESs) outperform other energy-storage devices in terms of power density and energy density, surpassing both batteries and fuel cells (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2017). Supercapacitors' great rate capability, extended life span, straightforward ideologies, and inexpensive preservation cost make them even more attractive (Obodo *et al.*, 2020; Chinnadurai *et al.*, 2020; Meng *et al.*, 2010). Based on the mechanisms of charging and storing, electrochemical double-layer capacitors (EDLCs) and pseudo-capacitors (PCs) can be distinguished (Zhou *et al.*, 2018; Zhao *et al.*, 2021). The former employs the electrochemical double-layer capacitances that result after basic charge separations within electrodes/electrolytes interfaces, while the latter uses the charge-transfer pseudo capacitance (PC) that results from the reversibility of Faradaic reactions that take place at the electrode surfaces (Zhang *et al.*, 2018; Bordbar *et al.*, 2017). If high

surface area materials like carbon nanotubes (CNTs), GO, rGO, etc (Chen *et al.*, 2017; Obodo *et al.*, 2020) are utilized as electrodes, EDLCs' capacitance value can be multiplied several times over when compared to traditional capacitors. The system undergoes no chemical or compositional change during the charge-storage process since there is no transference of charges across the interfaces (non-Faradaic) (Chu *et al.*, 2017). As a result, EDLCs can achieve long cycle lives and an identical great degree of reversibility in the repeating charge/discharge process. Nevertheless, the power and energy densities of EDLCs are modest. However, compared to EDLCs, the capacitance of PCs based on PC-exhibiting constituents like metal oxides and conducting polymers is 10 – 100 stretches greater, resulting in high power and energy densities (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Obodo *et al.*, 2024). Hence, producing merged electrodes that conglomerate Faradaic and non-Faradaic procedures to stock charges is mutually scientific and technologically significant (Obodo, *et al.*, 2020). Composite electrodes reduce the drawbacks and maximize the advantages of EDLCs and PCs (Obodo *et al.*, 2021) . As a result, it is possible to achieve greater energy and power densities than EDLCs while maintaining better cycle stability and cost compared to pseudo capacitors (De Wang *et al.*, 2021; Clyne *et al.*, 2019). As electrode materials for

EDLCs, carbon-based nanomaterials like graphene and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) have already gained considerable recognition. Because conducting polymers are inexpensive and simple to prepare, they have garnered more attention when it comes to materials that primarily display PCs. However, their limited reusability cycling (Obodo, et al., 2020; Obodo, et al, 2021; Obodo, et al, 2022) reduces its usage. Transition-metal oxides have shown to be more beneficial in this regard because of their stability and electrochemically reversible redox processes. RuO₂-grounded supercapacitor materials exhibit exceptionally high specific capacitance and high specific power amongst existing metal oxide materials; nonetheless, their cost and toxicity are prohibitive. Recent research has concentrated on several low-cost substitutes for RuO₂ (Chen *et al.*, 2019; Obodo *et al.*, 2024). Transition metal oxides (TMOs) like NiO, MnO₂, V₂O₅, Co₂O₃, TiO₂, and SnO₂

have been employed as electrode materials in electrochemical supercapacitor applications to reduce costs (Obodo *et al.*, 2021; Obodo *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, because of their larger surface area, the active materials' pseudo capacitance can be substantially changed at the nanoscale (Obodo *et al.*, 2022; Obodo *et al.*, 2022). However, it is imperative to grow a nanostructured material that offers an exceptional prospect in storing a large quantity of charge with a faster rate of charging, lower rate of discharging, stable, environmentally friendliness and cost-effective (Obodo *et al.*, 2021; Kim *et al.*, 2015). The objective of the work was to find an estimated molarity combination of Co₃(PO₄)₂@Mn(PO₄)₂ with an optimum performance for supercapacitor electrode application (Donne *et al.*, 2010). Figure 1 is a schematic diagram representing the synthesis techniques used for the fabrication of various Co₃(PO₄)₂@Mn(PO₄)₂ electrodes.

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of synthesis system, adapted with permission from Obodo, *et al.* (2020).

Materials and Methods

Materials for Synthesis

In this study, Cobalt nitrate ($\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) (Sigma Aldrich, 98.2%) and Nickel nitrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) (Sigma Aldrich, 96.8%) were used as a source of Co^+ and Ni^+ ions, respectively. Ammonium phosphate ($(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{PO}_4$) (Sigma Aldrich, 99.2%) was engaged as the reducing agent, double distilled water (H_2O) was used for the dissolution of various salts, rinsing, washing, etc. and sodium sulphate (Na_2SO_4) was employed for formation of electrolyte used during electrochemical characterizations. Fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) slides were used in the deposition of the electrodes. All the chemicals used are of analytical grade evaluated, and procured from Sigma Aldrich.

Synthesis of Electrodes

100 ml solutions of various salt baths were prepared, mixed in various molarities combinations and categorized as presented

in (Table 1). In each composition listed in (Table 1), they were placed on a magnetic stirrer and heater; 0.5 M $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{PO}_4$ solution was added via a burette as shown in Fig. 1 until the pH of the bath was 7 (neutral). The beaker containing the mixed (combined) salt baths and a cleaned FTO was inserted in it and was heated using a magnetic heater set at a temperature of 70 °C for 2 hours. After 2 hours, a pale green film was formed on FTO glass surfaces and as well a pale green precipitate on the bottom of the beaker. The same procedures adopted in CoMn 1 were engaged in the synthesis of CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4. Both the films (electrodes) and the precipitate were washed using distilled water, and dehydrated inside an oven using a temperature of 100 °C for 6 hours. Various electrodes and powder nanoparticles from the precipitate were stored in airtight containers for characterization. Table 1 reveals electrode compositions and labels.

Table 1 Electrodes compositions and labels

S/N	Salt Bath Compositions	Label
1.	100 ml 0.1 M $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ + 100 ml 0.1 M $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	CoMn 1
2.	100 ml 0.1 M $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ + 100 ml 0.2 M $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	CoMn 2
3.	100 ml 0.2 M $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ + 100 ml 0.1 M $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	CoMn 3
4.	100 ml 0.2 M $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ + 100 ml 0.2 M $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	CoMn 4

Electrodes Characterizations

The structural analysis of synthesized nanoparticles was examined using an X-ray diffractometer (XRD). The diffractometer is a BRUKER AXS (Germany), 40kV, 40mA,

D8 advanced X-ray diffractometer using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5425 \text{ \AA}$). It was carried out at 2θ ranges of 10 – 80 °. The optical features of various nanoparticles

were examined employing a UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer for absorption studies in a wavelength range of 300 nm – 1100 nm. The electrochemical investigations of various electrodes were considered utilizing a Biologic potentiostat (SP - 150) in a 1.0 M sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄) solution with three electrodes arrangement. Ag/AgCl was used as reference and graphite pole as the counter electrode.

Results and Discussion

XRD Analysis

The powder X-ray diffraction configurations shown in (Fig. 2) revealed the structural phases of these materials. These electrodes XRD diffraction peaks were indexed to Co₃O₄ with the JCPDS card of 001-1278 and MnO₂ with the JCPDS card of 003-1000 for CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4, respectively. CoMn 1 electrode sustained amalgamation of JCPDS 001-1278 and JCPDS 003-1000. CoMn 1

XRD diffraction crests were evident at 2θ angle = 40.71 °, 43.61 °, 46.05 ° and 61.04 ° assenting with hkl indices of (100), (002), (101) and (102). The CoMn 2 electrodes diffraction summits were shown at 2θ angle positions of 43.28 °, 45.50 ° and 47.55 ° with equivalent miller indices of (300), (310) and (311) respectively. Conversely, combinations of two metal oxides precursors, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 maintained the same diffraction crests and appeared at 43.28 °, 45.50 ° and 62.73 °, agreeing to (300), (002) and (102) hkl indices.

The estimated crystallite size (D) values are presented in Table 1 using Equation 1.

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \quad (1)$$

where K is a constant = 0.9, λ is the wavelength used = 1.5418 Å, θ = diffraction angle while β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM).

Table 2 Estimated crystallite sizes using XRD analysis.

S/N	Electrode	Crystal Systems	Crystallite Sizes (nm)
1.	CoMn 1	Hexagonal	40.45
2.	CoMn 2	Cubic	32.64
3.	CoMn 3	Hexagonal & Cubic	26.55
4.	CoMn 4	Hexagonal & Cubic	20.44

Figure 2 XRD Schematic illustration of various electrodes

Optical Nature of Electrodes

Light absorption features of these electrodes were studied using an ultra-violet (UV) visible spectrophotometer with a wavelength range of 300 - 1100 nm. The absorbance of nanostructured electrodes of CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 distinctions are 0.35 - 0.22, 0.23 - 0.12, 0.61 - 0.35, 0.42 - 0.23 and 0.51 - 0.25 a.u., respectively. The schemes of optical wavelength against the absorbances of different electrodes are presented in Fig. 3 (a). The electrode absorbance decreased as the wavelength increased toward the near-infrared region (NIR) and moved away from the visible portion of the electromagnetic spectrum. The electrode absorbance results indicate low absorbance properties. Equation 1 shows the optical

band gaps of these electrodes, which were determined using Tauc's equation given by Equation 2.

$$\alpha = A(h\nu - E_g)^n \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, in a straight band gap transition, the absorption band gap (E_g) is represented by the absorption band gap (α), and A is a constant, and n is $\frac{1}{2}$. The assessed band gap energies shown in (Fig. 3 (b)) for CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 electrodes are 2.43 eV, 2.20 eV, 1.73 eV and 2.40 eV, respectively. Band gap energy values varied for each electrode when the undeviating region of each plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ against $(h\nu)$ axis was extrapolated. These transition metal oxides worked together to create a lowered band gap energy that is appropriate for use in energy storage devices.

Figure 3 (a) Absorbance and (b) Band gap energy plots of CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 electrodes respectively

Electrochemical studies of the synthesized nanoparticles

Using an arrangement of three electrode structures for CV, GCD, and EIS employing a biologic potentiostat and software, the supercapacitors' manufactured electrodes were tested. In the charge and discharge scheme, a voltage range of 0.0 – 0.7 V was employed, with a current density of 1.0 A/g. The same setup that was employed in GCD studies was also applied to that of EIS. CV assessments were recorded between 0.0 and 0.7 0 V at various scan rates of 10, 20, and 30 mV/s. Figs. 4(a-c) displays the several CV plots that were obtained. These plots exhibited decent redox rings, indicating virtuous pseudocapacitive electrode materials. 0.1 M Potassium hydroxide (KOH) was used as the electrolytic solution in the tests that were conducted. Equation 3 was used to measure each electrode's specific capacitance (C_s).

$$C_s = \frac{\int_{V_c}^{V_a} I \times dV}{m \times S \times \Delta V} \quad (3)$$

where dV represents variations in potential values, I stands for current, m is the active mass of material laden, S stands for the scan rates and ΔV represents the difference in potential windows. For the CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3, and CoMn 4 electrodes, the computed values of specific capacitance from CV using a 1.0 mV/s scan were 465, 615, 1018, and 918 F/g, respectively. These findings demonstrate that, in comparison to other concentration combinations, the specific capacitance of the equal ratios of 0.2 M different salts is superior.

Real resistances in the electrochemical system as well as the kinetics of reactions were assessed using the EIS. The EIS was performed in the frequency range of 1.0 Hz–100.0 kHz at 25 °C in Fig. 4 (e). In EIS analysis, the constant phase element (CPE) equivalent electrical circuit model was utilized as shown in Fig. 4 (f). It matched flawlessly when used to estimate the

working electrode and electrolyte resistances from the Nyquist plot. These films have working electrode resistances (R_w) of 0.02 Ω , 0.08 Ω , 0.09 Ω , and 1.08 Ω for CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3, and CoMn 4 electrodes, respectively; and electrolyte resistances (R_e) of 8.0 Ω , 12.0 Ω , 17.0 Ω , and 20.0 Ω . These films' Nyquist spectra

did not show a half circle, which suggests that the films have a decreased charge transfer resistance and excellent supercapacitive performance (Obodo, et al, 2024). The results showed that these films had excellent cycling characteristics, making them a promising option for supercapacitor electrodes.

Figure 4 CV Plots of (a) CoMn 1 (b) CoMn 2 (c) CoMn 3 and (d) CoMn 4 (e) EIS for the electrodes and (f) CPE with the diffusion model respectively.

Likewise, GCD data and Equation 4 (Obodo, et al, 2024; Obodo, et al, 2019) were used to determine the specific capacitance of different electrodes and its plots shown in Fig. 5.

$$C_s = \frac{I}{m \times \frac{dV}{dt}} \quad (4)$$

where I stand for current for the GCD analysis, $\frac{dV}{dt}$ is the GCD tangent while m represents the loaded mass. Estimated C_s from GCD quantities were 575, 858, 1128 and 997 F/g for CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 electrodes, correspondingly employing 1.0 A/g current density. In GCD tests, the same specific capacitance trend that was observed in CV testing was preserved. Various energy (E_d) and power (P_d) densities of the electrodes were also estimated using Equations 5 and 6 (Obodo, et al, 2021; Obodo, et al, 2020; Obodo, et al 2022)

$$E_d = 0.5 \times C_s \times (\Delta V)^2 \quad (5)$$

$$P_d = 3.6 \frac{E_d}{t_D} \quad (6)$$

where ΔV represents the potential window and t_D stands for discharge times. The estimated energy densities for CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 electrodes were 138.88, 232.71, 320.91 and 233.77 Wh/kg, respectively, while 18.67, 29.93, 37.55 and 27.76 W/kg were the calculated power densities gotten for CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 electrodes, respectively. The supercapacitor's resistance losses were what led to the little voltage drop that can be seen in the GCD graphs. After several cycles of charging and discharging, it typically has a considerable value; this is known as the "aging phenomenon" (Li, et al., 2019; Mehmood, et al, 2020, Muzaffar, et al, 2021).

Figure 5 GCD Plots of CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 electrodes respectively

Coulombic efficiency (η) which defines the efficiency as well as rate of charge transfer in electrode materials was estimated to determine the efficiency of electrodes. The estimated values of Coulombic efficiency were done using Equation 7 (Obodo, et al, 2022; Miller, et al, 2010; He, et al., 2016; Obodo, et al, 2022).

$$\eta = \frac{T_d}{T_c} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

where T_d and T_c represent discharge and charge time correspondingly. The values of the estimated coulombic efficiency from the GCD plot for CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 were 97.8%, 97.8%, 81.5% and 92.6%, respectively. Various outcomes revealed that fabricated electrodes have pronounced efficiencies and are beneficial when used as electrode material.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

CoMn 1, CoMn 2, CoMn 3 and CoMn 4 electrodes were successfully synthesized using the hydrothermal method to fabricate electrodes on FTO substrates. Relatively low-cost chemicals and synthesis techniques were used to modify the morphological, structural, optical and electrochemical properties of the electrodes. The hydrothermal method is an easy and affordable technique for synthesizing high-quality electrodes. The synergistic effects

that exist between the constituents of various metal oxides created new composites with improved and enhanced properties. The electrochemical behavior from studies using CV, GCD and EIS, showed that the fabricated electrodes had remarkable specific capacitances from CV and GCD. The EIS studies showed that the fabricated electrodes had small resistances, which suggests that these electrodes possessed high conductivity and small resistance.

Recommendations

1. Further research is needed to determine the ideal ratio of $\text{Co}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and $\text{Mn}(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in the composite for maximizing electrochemical performance. This optimization can be achieved through a systematic variation of composition.
2. The design of the electrode architecture, including electrode thickness and porosity, can significantly affect the performance of supercapacitors. Researchers should explore different electrode architectures to improve the accessibility of active sites.
3. Surface modification techniques, such as the introduction of conductive polymers or carbon-based materials, should be investigated to further enhance the electrical conductivity of the

Co₃(PO₄)₂@Mn(PO₄)₂ composites, which can boost their charging-discharging performance.

Author's Contribution

Authors: ORM, AJN, EJM, OPC and EUC synthesized the nanomaterials, fabricated various electrodes, carried out the characterizations and analyzed the results., ECU, OC, OE, MC and DMO worked on the manuscript's editing. The data were conceptualized, proofread and confirmed by AI and MM,

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